

Development of SiC nano-particle/Mg₂Si thermoelectric composites

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Introduction

Thermoelectric (TE) materials Mg₂Si

Thermoelectric materials could play an important role in a global sustainable energy solution. Mg₂Si has characteristics such as

- ✓ Abundant element on earth
- ✓ Non-toxicity
- ✓ High power generation efficiency around 873 K^[1].
- ✓ Brittle failure behavior

Automobile applications

Improvement of fracture toughness is necessary.

Particle dispersed composites^[2]

Suppression crack propagation by addition of secondary phase.

Improvement of fracture toughness

Problems of intergranular composites

When the reinforcement dispersed at grain boundaries

Grain boundary scattering effect is increase

The reinforcement must be dispersed within grains.

[1] J. Zhao et al., *J. Mater. Chem. A*, **3**, 19774-19782, (2015).
[2] K. Niihara et al., *J CERAM SOC JAPAN*, **99**, 974-982, (1981).
[3] J. de Boor et al., *Act. Mater.*, **77**, 68-75(2014)

Objective

The aim of this study is to improve toughness without reducing TE properties of Mg₂Si.

In this study

- Fabrication of intragranular SiC nano-particle/Mg₂Si composites by melting process.
- Investigation of intragranular SiC effect on mechanical and TE properties of Mg₂Si.

Experimental procedure

1. Materials

2. Test methods

Mechanical properties

- Young's modulus: Ultrasonic pulse method
- Fracture toughness: Indentation fracture methods

$$K_c = 0.026 \frac{E^{1/2} P^{1/2} a}{c^{3/2}}$$

E: Young's modulus (GPa)
P: Indentation load (N)
A: Half length of average indentation diagonal (μm)
c: Half length of average crack length (μm)

TE properties

- Seebeck coefficient S: Thermoelectric power measurement
- Electrical Conductivity σ : Four-terminal method
- Thermal Conductivity κ : Laser flash method
- Figure of Merit ZT

$$ZT = \frac{S^2 \sigma}{\kappa} T$$

Results & Discussion

1. Microstructure of intragranular SiCnp / Mg₂Si

The microstructure of as-melted specimen

SiC nano-particles are incorporated Mg₂Si grains.

The microstructure of as-sintered specimen

Typical SEM image of as-sintered Mg₂Si specimen

Intragranular SiC nano-particle / Mg₂Si composites are successfully fabricated.

XRD profile of as-sintered Mg₂Si specimen

MgO has a negative effect on TE properties.
Mg₂Si + O₂ → 2MgO + Si above 723 K

[4] J. Tani et al., *IOP Conf. Ser.: Mater. Sci. Eng.*, **18**, 140213, (2011).

2. Mechanical and TE properties of intragranular SiCnp/Mg₂Si

Fracture toughness

SiC nano-particles deflect crack propagation → K_c 0.64 → 1.15 MPa·m^{1/2}.

Charge carriers transport properties

Temperature dependence of Hall mobility and electrical conductivity

Intragranular composites have a positive effect on charge carriers transport.

Relationship between toughness and TE performance.

Relationship between normalized ZT and normalized toughness

Improvement of toughness without reducing ZT is realized by intragranular reinforcement.

Conclusions

- Intragranular composites with SiC nano-particles incorporated within Mg₂Si grains were successfully fabricated by using SiC incorporated Mg₂Si granules.
- The fracture toughness of the intragranular composites increased as the SiC content increased. It was reached 1.15 MPa·m^{1/2}, which is 1.80 times larger than Pure Mg₂Si and the main toughening mechanism were crack deflection.
- Incorporating reinforcement within the Mg₂Si particles proved an effective way to improve toughness without reducing TE properties when adding a reinforcing phase compared with intergranular composites.
- Even if relatively high amount of reinforcement is introduced into Mg₂Si, the improvement of fracture toughness without reducing ZT is realized by intragranular reinforcement.

[5] K. Yin et al., *Scr. Mater.*, **126**, 1-5, (2017). [6] G. Kim et al., *Ceram. Int.*, **43**, 12979-12982, (2017).